

Studies in Aryne Chemistry : Part I. Reaction of Dehydrobenzene with Phenols

R. S. PAL, R. P. SHARMA and M. M. BOKADIA

School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain

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Benzenediazonium-2-carboxylate on treatment in neutral media with phenol afforded biphenyl and biphenyl ether. With cresols it gave biphenyl, corresponding biphenyl ethers and benzcoumarins.

THE fusion of aryl halides and sulphonates with alkalis to give phenols¹⁻³ and other rearranged products^{1,4} is indicative of dehydrobenzene mechanism⁴⁻⁷. In all such reactions the medium was throughout basic. In the present investigation the reactions of phenol, *o*-*m*- and *p*-cresols with dehydrobenzene have been studied in neutral media.

Reaction with Phenol: Benzenediazonium-2-carboxylate (I) on treatment with phenol in dry benzene afforded biphenyl and biphenyl ether. However, when THF was used as solvent, biphenyl ether was obtained as the sole reaction product.

Reaction with Cresols: Benzenediazonium-2-carboxylate, on treatment with *o*-, *m*- and *p*-cresols in dry benzene afforded biphenyl, corresponding biphenyl ether (II) and benzcoumarins (III) presumably through the intermediacy of the zwitterion. The formation of (III) may be through (Ib)⁸⁻¹⁰ and the reaction may be rationalized as in Chart 1.

Experimental

A. R. Samples of phenol, ortho, meta and para-cresols were employed. The purity of all the starting materials as well as that of the reaction products was confirmed by TLC. All the solvents were purified by the usual procedures. Anhydrous magnesium sulphate was employed for drying. Alumina grade II prepared by adding 3 ml. of water per 100 g. of alumina grade I and shaking thoroughly was used throughout. All the b.p.s. and m.p.s. are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded as liquid film for liquids and as nujol mull or KBr pellet in case of solids, on Perkin Elmer Infracord 221. The NMR spectra were taken using a Varian A-60 (60 MC) and HA-100 (100 MC) instruments with TMS as internal reference and CDCl₃ as solvent. The Mass spectra were determined on a RMU-7 instrument.

Reaction of Benzenediazonium-2-Carboxylate with Phenol:

(A) **Benzene as reaction medium:** Dry benzenediazonium-2-carboxylate (I) (2.0 g.) (prepared from 3.4 g

III a, R₂ = R₃ = H; R₁ = CH₃
 III b, R₁ = R₃ = H; R₂ = CH₃
 III c, R₁ = R₂ = H; R₃ = CH₃

II a, R₂ = R₃ = H; R₁ = CH₃
 II b, R₁ = R₃ = H; R₂ = CH₃
 II c, R₁ = R₂ = H; R₃ = CH₃

of anthranilic acid) was added to a solution of phenol (1.60 g) in dry benzene (75 ml.) and the suspension was stirred at 60°-70° for 6 hrs. and kept at room temperature for 24 hr. The reaction mixture was washed with 10% (50 ml.) NaOH solution, and with water (3 x 25). The benzene layer was dried and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The dark brown residue obtained was chromatographed over alumina grade II (60.0 g) and the following fractions were collected.

- (a) Elutions with Pet ether : Benzene (3 : 1, v/v) afforded (0.28 g) biphenyl, colorless solid, m. p. 68°-70° whose mixed m. p. with the authentic sample of biphenyl showed no depression.
- (b) Elutions with Pet. ether : Ben (1 : 1, v/v) gave (0.12 g) colorless solid, m. p. 27°-28° (lit^{1,2} for biphenyl ether 28°). It gave no color reaction with FeCl₃ and was characterised as biphenyl ether, by comparison of I. R. spectra with that of an authentic sample.

(B) *Tetrahydrofuran (THF) as reaction medium* : When THF was used in place of dry benzene, biphenyl ether (0.15 g) was obtained as the sole reaction product.

Reaction of Benzenediazonium-2-carboxylate with Cresols : The study was made by treating cresol (2.0 g) with benzenediazonium-2-carboxylate (2.0 g) in dry benzene, following the procedure (A) above described under phenol.

With O-Cresol : When (I) was treated with O-Cresol, it afforded (a) biphenyl (0.19 g), (b) a biphenyl ether derivative (IIa), as colorless liquid distilling at 115°-120°/1 mm.; on cooling it solidified. (Lit^{1,3} for IIa m. p. 22°, b. p. 267/738 mm). Its elemental analysis and I. R. spectrum were consistent with structure proposed, (c) colorless needles (IIIa, 0.11 g) m. p. 133-134°C (Found C, 80.0 ; H, 4.90 ; C₁₄H₁₀O₂ requires C, 80.0 ; H, 4.76%).

IR (KBr) : Strong bands at 1730 cm⁻¹ (δ -lactone) carboxyl stretching 1590 (aromatic) C=C stretching 1240, 1200 cm⁻¹ (-C-O-stretching) 755 cm⁻¹. Aromatic -C-H ; out of plane bending.

NMR : 1.5-2.7 τ (7H, aromatic), 7.5 τ (3H, methyl group attached to benzene ring).

Mass : m/e is at 210. C₁₄H₁₀O₂ requires 210.

With m-Cresol : (I) with m-cresol afforded (a) biphenyl ; (b) biphenyl ether derivative (II b, 0.11 g) as a colorless liquid distilled at 130-135°/1.5 mm. (Lit^{1,3} b. p. 274°/738 mm). The structure was consistent with analytical data and I. R. spectra, (c) colorless needles (from methanol) of (IIIb, 0.09g), m.p. 117°-118°.

(Found C, 79.87 ; H, 4.51 ; C₁₄H₁₀O₂ requires C, 80.0 ; H, 4.76%)

IR (KBr) : Strong bands at 1740 cm⁻¹ (δ -lactone) C=O stretching 1600 cm⁻¹ (aromatic C=C stretching

1200 cm⁻¹ (-C-O-stretching) 745 and 685 cm⁻¹ ; -C-H out of plane bending.

With p-cresol : Likewise (I) with p-cresol afforded (a) biphenyl (0.20g) ; (b) biphenyl ether derivative (II c, 0.17 g) as a liquid b. p 145°-150°/2 mm. (lit^{1,3} for IIc, b. p. 277°-8°/745 mm). The structure was further confirmed by elemental and spectral (I. R.) analyses, (c) colorless needles (from methanol) of (IIIc, 0.15 g) having m. p. 127°-29°.

(Found C, 80.0 ; H, 4.66 ; C₁₄H₁₀O₂ requires C, 80.0 ; H, 4.76%).

IR : 1730 Cm⁻¹ (δ -lactone carbonyl stretching) 1603 Cm⁻¹ aromatic C=C, stretching 1240, 1200 cm⁻¹ (-C-O-stretching), 765, 705 and 670 cm⁻¹. C-4 out of plane bending.

NMR : 1.50 - 2.75 τ (7H, aromatic), singlet at 7.5 τ (3H, methyl protons).

Mass : m/e is 210, C₁₄H₁₀O₂ requires 210.

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